

INFLUENCE OF COATINGS ON WOOD'S MOISTURE BUFFER CAPACITY

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1. INTRODUCTION

As a hygroscopic material, wood's moisture content (MC) fluctuates in response to changes in the surrounding climate. Given that real-world conditions are constantly shifting and due to the slow sorption process, wood rarely achieves a stable hygrothermal balance with its environment. This ability of wood to absorb and release moisture, thereby moderating fluctuations in indoor relative humidity (RH), is known as its moisture buffer capacity (MBC) [1]. Utilizing the MBC can be advantageous for enhancing indoor climate stability [e.g. 2] and promoting energy efficiency [e.g. 3]. Regarding wood, previous studies have investigated the MBC of various wood products, such as solid wood [e.g. 4], plywood [e.g. 5], paneling [e.g. 6], wood-based insulated panels [e.g. 7] and furniture [e.g. 8]. The challenge of fully utilizing wood's MBC is that wood products are usually coated for improving their aesthetics and technical properties; these coatings can diminish the MBC [e.g. 9]. Previous research has revealed the importance of further investigation to improve the understanding of coating compositions on the MBC of wood and wood-based products.

The objective of our study was to determine the influence of a wide range of coatings on the MBC of spruce as well as on the indoor RH of a model room in a residential building.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The water vapor permeability and MBC of clearwood specimens made from Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) coated with seven commercial coatings were determined. Both tests included uncoated control samples. Additionally, the MBC of gypsum and spruce clad with gypsum was measured. For a better understanding of the moisture dynamics, the sorption properties of three of the seven coatings were analyzed using a Dynamic Vapor Sorption device (DVS). The minimum and maximum measured Sd-values were utilized in hygrothermal models to determine the moisture dynamics at room level.

Table 1. Overview of the materials used in the water vapor permeability test, the MBC-test and the DVS-analysis (X = included). Application was carried out according to the producers' specifications. The FR-stain (G) is a certified Euroclass B-s1, d0 treatment for CLT at the application rate used in this study.

MATERIAL	NO. OF COATS	MEAN APPLICATION RATE, WET [g/m ²] (WATER PERMEABILITY/MBC)	MEAN FILM THICKNESS [μ] (WATER PERMEABILITY/MBC)	VAPOR PERMEABILITY	MBC	DVS	
A	Waterborne PUD modified alkyd	1	135/153	45/50	X	X	
B	Waterborne alkyd	1	79/84	-	X	X	X
C	Solventborne PUD reinforced alkyd	1	46/47	-	X	X	
D	Waterborne oil emulsion	1	65/69	10/10	X	X	
E	Hardwax oil	1	26/27	5/5	X	X	
F	Silicate	2	261/260	60/60	X	X	X

G	FR-stain	4	358/348	-	X	X	X
H	Spruce				X	X	
I	Gypsum					X	
J	Spruce + gypsum					X	

The water vapor permeability, expressed as Sd-value, was determined in a dry-cup test according to EN ISO 7783:2018, applying a climate gradient of 3 %RH/50 %RH at 23 °C. For each material, five replicates with a diameter of 98 mm were used.

The MBC, expressed as the Practical Moisture Buffer Value (MBV), was gravimetrically determined on clearwood specimens according to the NORDTEST protocol (10). The exposed area of the specimens was 100 x 100 mm². The spruce specimens were 20 mm thick, the gypsum plasterboard 12.5 mm. Four replicates were used for each material.

A DVS device (VSorp Enhanced, ProUmid GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) was used for the analysis of equilibrium moisture content (EMC) at 25°C with 10% humidity steps from 0% to 90%, to 95%, and from 90% back to 0% relative humidity (absorption and desorption isotherm). Prior to the analysis, the coating samples were dried at 60 °C under a vacuum of 20 mbar, and at 103 °C subsequently to the DVS-analysis.

To model the moisture dynamics at room level, the hygrothermal energy simulation tool WUFI® Plus (IBP, F. 2019, 3.2.0 Ed.) was used. The room is part of a residential building with an area of 5 x 10 m² (Figure 1). The relevant specifications regarding the indoor environment and the heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) system were followed as described in SN-NSPEK 3031:2020 [11]. Two building systems were considered: (i) a CLT/solid timber wall system used for both the exterior and interior walls, and (ii) a conventional stud wall system as the exterior wall and concrete as the internal wall. All external walls are insulated, having a U-value of 0.18 W/m²K. In total, six different wall designs were simulated (Tab. 2). Scenario #5 was included in the analysis to investigate the possible influence of CLT's glue lines in the frontal plane. This wall design, for instance, represents CLT where the layers are connected by fasteners instead of glue.

Figure 1. 3D-view of the room model. The two sides with windows are external walls while the other two sides are internal walls. The long façade is oriented to the south, the short façade towards the east.

Table 2. Overview of the wall materials

SCENARIO	EXTRNAL HOUSE WALL	INTERNAL HOUSE WALL
#1	Insulated CLT without coating	Non-insulated CLT without coating
#2	Insulated CLT with gypsum as interior finish	Non-insulated CLT with gypsum as interior finish
#3	Insulated CLT with interior coating (Sd of 0.01 m)	Non-insulated CLT with interior coating (Sd of 0.01 m)
#4	Insulated CLT with interior coating (Sd of 0.59 m)	Non-insulated CLT with interior coating (Sd of 0.59 m)
#5	Insulated wall in solid timber	Non-Insulated wall in solid timber
#6	Insulated stud wall with wood panel as exterior cladding and gypsum board as interior cladding	Non-insulated concrete wall with mortar on both surfaces

The HVAC-system was assumed to have no humidification and dehumidification. Two different functions were considered: (i) with moisture recovery and ii) without moisture recovery.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 presents the Sd-values of the seven coatings as well as the MBV and their classification of spruce, gypsum, and spruce clad with a gypsum. The Sd-values of five out of the seven coatings investigated was below 0.1 m. The low values align with findings of Gröll and Truskaller [12] who measured the water vapor permeability of 22 non-film forming and low-build wood coatings. An MBV of 0.86 classifies the MBC of uncoated spruce as “moderate” and of CLT clad with gypsum as “limited”. The MBV of untreated Norway spruce reported in the literature ranges from 0.91 [9] to 1.36 [4,10]. The coatings reduced the MBV by up to 74 % (hard wax oil) and as little as 7% (waterborne alkyd and silicate). A 7 % reduction is relatively low compared to those reported in other studies on wood coatings [9,13,14].

Table 3. Sd-values and MBV_{practical} of the tested materials

MATERIAL	S _d [m]	MBV [g/m ² %RH]	MBV-CLASS
A Waterborne PUD modified alkyd	0.10	0.16	Negligible
B Waterborne alkyd	0.03	0.83	Moderate
C Solventborne PUD reinforced alkyd	0.03	0.60	Moderate
D Waterborne oil emulsion	0.04	0.23	Limited
E Hardwax oil	0.03	0.37	Limited
F Silicate	0.02	0.83	Moderate
G FR-stain	0.59	1.29	Good
H Spruce		0.89	Moderate
I Gypsum		0.25	Limited
J Spruce + gypsum		0.28	Limited

Spruce coated with the FR-stain exhibited an even higher MBV than uncoated spruce, despite being the least vapor-permeable of all the coatings analyzed (Tab. 3). This can be attributed to the pronounced hygroscopicity of the FR-stain, which significantly exceeds that of the other three coatings in the DVS-analysis (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Sorption curves of coating B, F, and G measured in the DVS-analysis

Figures 3A and 3B show the minimum and maximum RH in the simulated room when the HVAC-system does not include humidification/dehumidification. Regardless of whether moisture recovery is included in the HVAC-system, the coatings reduce the MBC of wood (scenarios #3 and #4). This is particularly true for the FR-stain. Based on the MBV (Table 3), the CLT element coated with the FR-stain (scenario #4) should have buffered the RH in the model room most effectively. However, the WUFI[®] Plus simulations take into account the Sd-values and not the MBV. In this context, the comparatively high Sd-value of the FR-stain (0.59 m) negatively impacts the simulations, despite the MBV of 1.61 W/(m²K) suggesting otherwise.

Figure 3. Indoor RH in a room with different wall materials (scenario 1-6, see Table 2) without moisture recovery (A) and with moisture recovery (B).

The wall design with uncoated wood and without gypsum revealed the smallest difference between maximum and minimum RH (Figure 3A and B, scenarios #1 and #5). This behavior is beneficial for passive control of the indoor environment. In contrast, the maximum RH was highest in scenarios #2 and #6, which involved the CLT-element clad with a gypsum board and the stud wall with the gypsum board on the interior. The opposite picture is observed for the minimum RH: the highest values were seen in scenarios #1 and #5 whereas the lowest values were found for scenarios #2 and #6.

The MBC of wood increases when moisture recovery is included in the HVAC-system (Figure 3B). In scenario #5 (the most beneficial), the maximum RH is 9.4% lower and the minimum RH is 4.6% higher compared to scenario #6 (the least beneficial). Currently, most HVAC systems incorporate only heat recovery without moisture recovery. Our results suggest that including moisture recovery would help maximize the full potential of wood's MBC.

4. CONCLUSION

The influence of wood coatings on MBC varies strongly dependent on the coating composition. In our study, the best performing coatings resulted in a reduction of only 7%. Gypsum was found to decrease the MBC of spruce by 72%. From the practical standpoint, replacing gypsum is challenging in applications with strict fire safety requirements. To some extent, this could be addressed by using an FR-stain, which increased the moisture buffer value (MBV) by 45% compared to untreated spruce. However, it's important to note that even the best FR treatment can only improve the fire performance of wood from Euroclass D to B, but not to A.

Finally, the results for the FR-stain highlight a weakness in the methodology for quantifying MBC and simulating its impact on the indoor environment. A coating's MBV may be high due to its hygroscopicity, but if its water vapor permeability is low, this can affect its actual performance.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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